

Equilibrium Core Analysis of HTR-PM Based on High-Fidelity Multi-Physics Coupling

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ABSTRACT

The equilibrium core is the final stable state of the online refueling process in pebble-bed high-temperature gas-cooled reactors (HTGRs). Traditional methods often rely on approximations, such as spatial homogenization, to handle the pebble bed geometry. While sufficient for some engineering applications, these methods lack simulation accuracy. To address this issue, this paper utilizes a high-fidelity multi-physics coupling framework—based on the Monte Carlo (MC) method, Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) (using a porous media approximation coupled with a single-pebble heat conduction model), and the Discrete Element Method (DEM)—to simulate the core refueling process for the HTR-PM. This work obtained equilibrium core results with single-pebble resolution and successfully achieved convergence for the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}), power distribution, temperature distribution, burnup distribution, and nuclide concentration distributions. To select an optimal refueling scheme, a simplified matrix-iterative model was proposed to rapidly evaluate and compare the convergence behavior of different strategies. Through this comparison, a “fixed replacement proportion” scheme was identified as having superior convergence properties. Using this scheme, the simulation converged to an equilibrium core state in approximately 20 refueling cycles, which required about 35 days of computation time.

Keywords: HTR-PM, Equilibrium Core, Multi-Physics Coupling, High-Fidelity, Pebble-Bed Reactor

1. INTRODUCTION

As a representative of Generation IV advanced nuclear energy systems, the High-Temperature Gas-Cooled Reactor (HTGR) has gained widespread recognition for its inherent safety and high-temperature characteristics. The pebble-bed modular high-temperature gas-cooled reactor (HTR-PM) demonstration project, in particular, has entered commercial operation, marking a significant achievement for China in this field. The core structure of the HTR-PM is extremely complex, featuring a “double heterogeneity”: the core consists of approximately 420,000 randomly packed spherical fuel pebbles, and each pebble contains about 10,000 randomly arranged fuel particles [1, 2]. Concurrently, the fuel pebbles continuously move downward, exit from the bottom, and undergo online refueling, where pebbles that have reached their target discharge burnup are replaced with fresh ones, while the rest are returned to the top of the core [3]. After a period of online refueling, the reactor transitions from its initial core loading (containing about 50,000 fuel pebbles and 290,000 graphite pebbles [4]) to a stable state where approximately 420,000 fuel pebbles with varying burnup levels are mixed, known as the equilibrium core. Due to this complexity, current simulation studies of the equilibrium core often rely on approximations, and there is a lack of high-fidelity coupled neutronics-thermals-pebble flow analysis capable of achieving single-pebble resolution. Furthermore, most existing research has only achieved convergence for global parameters like the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}), not for the detailed distribution of nuclide concentrations within the core. This paper aims to address this gap by using high-fidelity multi-physics coupling to obtain a strictly converged equilibrium core result for the HTR-PM.

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2. HIGH-FIDELITY MULTI-PHYSICS COUPLING FRAMEWORK

This research is based on a previously established high-fidelity coupling framework for the simulation of neutron physics, thermal-hydraulics, and pebble flow in pebble-bed reactors [5].

2.1. Neutron Physics

The framework employs the Monte Carlo (MC) method for neutron physics calculations using the open-source code OpenMC [6]. The MC method simulates the lifecycle of a large number of neutrons to calculate core parameters without needing to discretize geometry, neutron energy, or direction, thus enabling high-fidelity calculations. To overcome the high memory and computational time costs associated with high-fidelity models, the framework utilizes a virtual lattice optimization technique [7], which effectively reduces resource consumption and facilitates the extraction of single-pebble resolution results.

2.2. Thermal-Hydraulics

The framework uses the open-source Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) code OpenFOAM for thermal-hydraulic calculations [8]. While CFD can theoretically model the pebble bed geometry explicitly, the computational cost is prohibitive. Research has shown that simulating a core with 350,000 fuel pebbles using an explicit geometry model would require an unacceptable amount of time, even using all of the 27648 GPUs on the Summit supercomputer [9]. Therefore, the framework adopts a porous media approximation for the core geometry, coupled with a one-dimensional heat conduction model for each individual fuel pebble to obtain thermal-hydraulic results with single-pebble resolution.

2.3. Pebble Flow

The framework uses the LAMMPS code to perform Discrete Element Method (DEM) simulations of pebble flow [10]. DEM simulates the motion of each pebble based on classical mechanics, providing position and velocity information with single-pebble resolution. This method is mature, and the time required to simulate the passage of all pebbles through the HTR-PM core is on the order of hours, which meets the computational demands of the study.

2.4. Neutronics/Thermal-Hydraulics/Pebble-Flow Coupling

The framework uses an external coupling method to link the different physics fields. As shown in Figure 1, the process begins with iterative coupled calculations between OpenMC and OpenFOAM to obtain converged power and temperature distributions for the current time step. Following this, OpenMC performs the burnup calculation for that time step. In the next time step, OpenMC first updates the positions of all fuel pebbles using the results from the LAMMPS pebble flow simulation before beginning a new round of coupled neutronics and thermal-hydraulics calculations. Notably, since the influence of neutronics and thermal-hydraulics on pebble flow is negligible, the LAMMPS simulation can be completed independently before the main coupling loop begins.

3. HTR-PM HIGH-FIDELITY MODELING

3.1. Neutron Physics Model

The geometry of the high-fidelity MC model was based on the HTR-PM first criticality model, featuring explicit modeling of 420,000 fuel pebbles and the fuel particles within them. To simplify the model, OpenMC's "repeated structure" capability was used, meaning the internal arrangement of fuel particles is identical for every pebble. Studies have shown that the impact of this simplification is negligible

Figure 1. High-fidelity neutronics/thermal-hydraulics/pebble-flow coupling framework .

[4, 11] . To validate the model, a verification model was built based on the first criticality specifications; its calculated k_{eff} of 0.99854 ± 0.00010 showed excellent agreement with the critical value of 1 .

3.2. Thermal-Hydraulics Model

The porous media model of the core utilizes a structured cylindrical mesh divided into 10 radial layers, 25 circumferential layers, and 150 axial layers, for a total of 37,500 cells . A grid independence test confirmed that this mesh resolution is sufficient to obtain well-converged results for this case . Furthermore, using the equilibrium core power distribution as input, the model's calculated maximum helium outlet temperature of approximately 1176 K agreed well with the reference value of 1191 K, validating the model's accuracy .

3.3. Pebble Flow Model

The DEM pebble flow model parameters were based on existing research . To prevent geometric overlaps in the coupled MC model, the pebble diameter in the DEM simulation was increased by a negligible 0.002 cm from the true value of 6 cm . This adjustment did not affect the final packing fraction, which remained at the reference value of 61The calculated radial distribution of the packing fraction showed excellent agreement with experimental data [12] , further validating the model .

4. SELECTION OF REFUELING SCHEME

Directly simulating the entire Running-in Phase from the initial core loading to the equilibrium state is computationally prohibitive and of limited value, as the actual refueling strategy is unknown . Therefore, this study aimed to design a hypothetical refueling process that could rapidly converge to the equilibrium state .

4.1. Matrix-Iterative Model for Scheme Evaluation

To quickly evaluate the convergence speed of different refueling schemes, a simplified, low-cost model was developed. This model represents the burnup distribution of fuel pebbles entering the core as a 90-dimensional vector, corresponding to 90 burnup intervals from 0 to 90 MWD/kgU. The burnup increase a pebble experiences in one pass depends on its initial burnup and the neutron flux level of the flow channel it passes through, described by the relation:

$$bt_1 = bt_0 + f(bt_0)p_i \quad (1)$$

where bt_0 is the burnup of the fuel pebble when it enters the core, bt_1 is the burnup when it leaves the core, i is the flow channel index, and p_i represents the neutron flux level of that channel. The function $f(bt_0)$ represents the correction factor for the burnup increase based on the initial burnup; specifically, it is the relationship between power and burnup depth under the same neutron flux. Tests on a single HTR-PM fuel pebble using OpenMC show that $f(b)$ approximately follows the quadratic relationship below:

$$\begin{aligned} f(b) &= \alpha b^2 + \beta b + \gamma \\ &= -2 \times 10^{-5} b^2 - 0.0079b + 1.3938, \quad R^2 = 0.9999 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Since the fuel pebbles entering the core are uniformly distributed among the flow channels, the burnup distribution at the top of any given channel, for instance, channel i , must be A :

$$A_i = A = [a_1, a_2, \dots, a_{90}] \quad (3)$$

Then, after this batch of fuel pebbles passes through the core once and the pebbles with a burnup greater than 90 MWD/kgU are replaced with new ones, the burnup distribution upon re-entry into the core is:

$$A'_i = [a'_1, a'_2, \dots, a'_{90}] \quad (4)$$

$$a'_1 = \sum_{k \in \{k | 90 < k + f(k)p_i\}} a_k \quad (5)$$

$$a'_j = \sum_{k \in \{k | j < k + f(k)p_i \leq j+1\}} a_k, \quad j > 1 \quad (6)$$

If the flow channels are defined such that the number of pebbles flowing through each channel per unit time is the same, then the loading burnup distribution for the next time step is the arithmetic mean of the distributions from all channels:

$$A' = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n A'_i \quad (7)$$

At this point, the loading burnup distribution between two adjacent time steps can be written as the following matrix iterative relationship:

$$A' = BA \quad (8)$$

While this model involves significant simplifications, it is sufficient for the purpose of rapidly comparing the convergence behavior of different schemes.

4.2. Evaluation of Refueling Schemes based on the Matrix-Iterative Model

4.2.1. Fixed Discharge Burnup

In this scheme, pebbles with a burnup exceeding 90 MWD/kgU are replaced with fresh fuel. Matrix iteration results showed that, regardless of the initial core state, this scheme required approximately 3000 refueling cycles to converge, making it computationally infeasible, which was shown in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Matrix calculation results of fuel replacement proportion.

4.2.2. Fixed Replacement Proportion

In this scheme, a fixed fraction (1/15) of the discharged pebbles with the highest burnup is replaced with fresh fuel in each cycle. This approach forces the core to quickly reach a state where pebbles that have made 1 to 15 passes are evenly mixed, thus accelerating the approach to equilibrium. Matrix iteration results confirmed that this scheme converges rapidly for two different initial core states as shown in Figure 3, in about 15 refueling cycles, which is far superior to the previous method.

Figure 3. Matrix calculation results when the burnup of initial fuel pebbles is 0 or uniformly distributed between 0 and 90 MWD/kgU.

4.3. Design of the Initial Core

To further accelerate convergence, a special initial core state was designed. A “quasi-equilibrium state” was constructed by first using the matrix-iterative model to calculate the converged loading burnup distribution. This distribution, combined with a reference power profile and single-pebble depletion

calculations (which relate nuclide content to burnup), was used to generate a full-core initial nuclide distribution that closely resembles the true equilibrium state. By starting the high-fidelity simulation from this quasi-equilibrium state and using the fixed replacement proportion scheme, a strictly converged equilibrium core is expected to be reached in approximately 15 refueling cycles.

5. HTR-PM EQUILIBRIUM CORE SIMULATION RESULTS

5.1. Convergence of Results

Based on the selected models and refueling scheme, a simulation of 20 refueling cycles was performed, taking approximately one month of computation time to reach an equilibrium core state. As shown in Figure 4, the effective multiplication factor (k_{eff}), core power distribution (represented by Shannon entropy), temperature distribution, and burnup distribution (Cs-137) all achieved convergence.

Figure 4. Convergence of k_{eff} and distribution results.

5.2. Analysis of HTR-PM Equilibrium Core Results

5.2.1. Power Distribution

As seen in Figure 5 (a), the single-pebble-accuracy power distribution is highly non-uniform. Even adjacent pebbles can have significantly different power levels due to large differences in their burnup. On a macroscopic level, the radial power profile is peaked in the center, while the axial power peak is shifted toward the upper part of the core due to temperature feedback from the top-to-bottom coolant flow. The maximum single-pebble power was 2.30 kW, which is below the safety limit of 3.5 kW.

Figure 5. Distribution results with the accuracy of single-pebble resolution.

5.2.2. Temperature Distribution

Radially, the helium and fuel pebble temperatures are highest in the center, consistent with the power distribution. Axially, temperatures are negatively correlated with height due to the top-to-bottom coolant flow. The maximum fuel temperature was approximately 1254 K, which is below the safety limit of 1473 K. The maximum helium outlet temperature was approximately 1198 K. The specific distribution can be referred in Figure 5 (b) (c).

5.2.3. Burnup Distribution

As shown in Figure 5 (d), the overall burnup is negatively correlated with height, as pebbles burn up while moving downwards. However, at the local level, the burnup distribution shows large fluctuations and no clear pattern. This is because each batch of pebbles loaded into the core is a mixture of pebbles with different numbers of passes, leading to a wide and well-mixed range of burnup values in the core. The maximum single-pebble burnup was 98.84 MWD/kgU, below the design limit of 100 MWD/kgU.

6. CONCLUSIONS

This paper established a high-fidelity neutronics/thermal-hydraulics/pebble-flow coupled simulation model for the HTR-PM core using the open-source codes OpenMC, OpenFOAM, and LAMMPS. To reduce the computational cost of reaching an equilibrium state, a matrix-iterative approximation method was proposed to rapidly evaluate the convergence speed of different refueling schemes. Through comparison, an optimized approach combining a "fixed replacement proportion" refueling scheme with a "quasi-equilibrium" initial core state was selected, proving capable of handling the demands of high-fidelity HTR-PM equilibrium core simulation. Using this methodology, a strictly converged equilibrium core was obtained, in which the effective multiplication factor, power distribution, temperature distribution, burnup distribution, and nuclide concentration distributions were all converged. The analysis showed that the core parameters in the equilibrium state align with physical expectations, and

key safety parameters such as maximum single-pebble power and peak fuel temperature remain within their design limits .

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